

THE ROLE OF THE INTERNET IN DISTANCE LEARNING

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Annotation: *This article discusses the role of the Internet in distance learning, the requirements for teachers in the process of using Internet technology in the learning process, the role of information and communication technologies in the educational process, the use of the Internet or They will talk about the main areas of use of distance learning, opportunities to use the moodle software package, the organization of distance learning courses.*

Keywords: *internet, chats, forums, e-mail, video conferencing, personal computers, video and audio equipment.*

Nowadays, progress is evolving and changing rapidly. Almost every minute there are changes, updates and surprises in different parts of the planet. Every day is spent under a strong flow of information. The flow of information haunts us everywhere, at home, at work, on the street and on vacation. Humans cannot function normally without the influence of information. Understanding and studying life takes place through the collection and assimilation of information. A person's level of knowledge is also determined by the amount of information that a person learns over a period of time.

The help of a computer system in learning, that is, in mastering certain types of information, is enormous. As the head of state said, "the tasks of in-depth teaching of special sciences, history of our country and world civilization, foreign languages and modern computer programs to children and youth have not yet been fully and

qualitatively solved." ¹One of the main tasks of our state is to educate the younger generation by overcoming such pressing problems.

That is why opening the way to modern knowledge, the effective use of new information technologies in improving education - has become a requirement of today. However, "the use of information technology in education is one of the most important issues for all science teachers today. Because information technology, especially the Internet, develops students' intellectual and critical thinking skills. It is possible to provide them with a certain amount of additional material via the Internet. It is important that students' use of Internet technology in the learning process is fully supervised by the teacher. In this process, the following requirements are set for teachers:

- 1) knowledge of computer literacy and use of Internet technologies;
- 2) organizing students' activities related to the search and analysis of necessary materials;
- 3) monitoring the stages of students' work on the Internet and assessing its quality ²"is making significant changes in the education system on the basis of several requirements.

In particular, the education system is creating sites for educational institutions and distance learning. The advantage and convenience of this system is that the student can study at any time, at work, on the street, on the bus, on vacation. Another advantage of these sites is that the duration of study is determined by the student, which means that the student can start studying at any time and master the

¹ Sh.Mirziyoev. Critical analysis, strict discipline - and personal responsibility - should be a daily rule of every leader. Tashkent - "Uzbekistan", 2017, p. 49.

² Baltaeva Anadjan Tadjibaevna. Students to the Heroes of the Artistic Work Non-Traditional that Teaches Critical Evaluation Lessons. International Journal on Orange Technologies. Vol. 3 No. 4 (2021): IJOT P. 294-300.

assignments under the supervision of the teacher. Assignment is determined by the completion of tests. The following materials are provided on these sites: textbooks, audio and video textbooks, online lessons (Internet), electronic libraries, multimedia tests and electronic textbooks.

Present demand is for a new learning environment, with the help of new information technologies, where you can learn from anywhere, connect with volunteer schools, and access information from anywhere in the world. The Internet can help us with this. Through the Internet, it can be seen that schools, colleges and educational institutions, where the education system was established, are now being merged into the evolving "virtual schools". This reduces the distance between educational institutions and maximizes the exchange of information. In this regard, distance learning has become popular in philological education as a very necessary and rapid form of teaching and learning. Distance learning is the process of interactive communication between listeners and teachers through the purpose, content, methods, teaching aids and Internet technologies of the learning process.

Distance education is a form of education based on the complex distance learning of all disciplines in the system of training specialists in a particular field, without a fixed place and time criteria for the learning process within the complex. Provides video and electronically published teaching materials that create an automated learning environment in distance learning, as well as teaching and testing tools (fully automated, complete software products) that function as a teacher.

Distance learning is defined by researchers and practitioners as follows: traditional and new information used in the delivery of learning material, independent learning, and the exchange of communication between teacher and student. is a synthetic, integral, social form of education in the widespread use of technologies and their technical means. Distance education is built for the same purposes as in the context of full-time education (if it is built on a curriculum that is appropriate for the curriculum), but the form of delivery of the material, teachers

and students, as well as of the form of interaction between the birds will be different. The basic didactic principles of this education are the same as other types of education, but the organizational principles of distance education are different, they are specific to distance education, because with form features, internet media opportunities, chats, forums, email, videoconferencing expressed. Its distinctive features are modularity, mastery of the role of the teacher, distance separation of the subjects of the learning process, virtual co-operation of education, the establishment of self-control over the control exercised by the teacher, modern as an example the use of special education technologies and tools.

The main areas of use of distance learning are:

- professional development of teachers in certain areas;
- preparation of schoolchildren for special subjects in the expert examination;
- preparation of schoolchildren for admission to certain educational institutions;
- organization of school education for students;
- additional education on interests;
- retraining;
- professional training.

Distance education differs from the form of distance learning in that a significant part of the material is not independently mastered, but is carried out in constant communication with the teacher, ie online consultations over the phone and the Internet, lectures and seminars. Also, the main differences between distance learning and distance learning are: -Constant communication with the teacher through the use of telecommunications, the ability to communicate with him promptly on any questions that arise. If we compare distance learning with full-time and part-time forms of education, distance learning is based on the use of personal computers, video and audio technology, space and fiber-optic technology, distance learning and distance learning with information technology. It can be seen as a new

stage in the development of science. Comparing distance learning with full-time and part-time forms of education, distance learning, personal computers, video and audio technology, space and optical fiber technology-based learning, the development of distance and full-time education with information technology we are right in saying that it is a new stage. In many countries around the world, distance learning is organized using the Moodle software package. Because distance education has proved its importance and necessity. In accordance with the order of the Minister of Higher and Secondary Special Education of March 27, 2020 "On the introduction of distance learning in higher education institutions", the existing universities in our country created unit technologies and launched its own sites. Even in order to effectively organize distance learning courses, qualified teachers with IT skills have been formed and distance learning plans and programs have been developed. The ZOOM social network has been used wisely as a distance learning platform for the convenience of its listeners. Distance learning courses offer the following benefits to students: online registration without unnecessary hassle; improves skills without leaving the place of work and residence; saves extra costs; saves extra time. The state pays special attention to the implementation of e-learning resources and websites of educational institutions created for educational institutions in the educational process. Cataloging of sites created for educational institutions, promotion of e-textbooks prepared in educational institutions of the republic among all educational institutions is important and complex. Therefore, by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the information and educational portal www.ziyonet.uz was launched and educational resources for all educational institutions were posted on this portal.

Conclusion. So, bottom line is that the Internet has a huge role to play in education. The breadth and variety of educational services provided through the distance education system make the quality of education more effective. The development of distance education will further improve the development of

information and telecommunications technologies. In the process of distance learning, editing texts, solving computer-based translation from one language to another, raising the level of computer literacy, teaching logical, consistent thinking, the formation of theoretical knowledge in them and the development of students' self-knowledge. in the formation of skills in the field, as well as in the formation of in-depth knowledge of computer linguistics in modular philologists, mastering the principles of computer linguistics, the correct orientation of knowledge in the construction of mathematical models, formalization The Internet can play an important role in developing the ability to apply knowledge in the field, teaching thinking based on mathematical logic, creating computer programs for language and literature, creating algorithms and computer programs.

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